

TEACHING PROFICIENCY AND PERFORMANCE OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. The study determined the level of teaching proficiency and the level of performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools. This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the level of teaching proficiency was high while the level of performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools was also high. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the teaching proficiency have a strong positive correlation to the performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of teaching proficiency on performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools: Lesson Planning and Content. It is suggested that the teachers handling professional subjects must continuously update their knowledge and skills so they can provide the competencies needed by the pre-service teachers in teaching. It also recommended the cooperating teacher-respondents must continue upgrading through postgraduate education. Since the cooperating teachers are responsible for training and mentoring the pre-service teachers, they must serve as a model to them.

KEY WORDS

1. Teaching proficiency.
2. performance of pre-service teachers.
3. Lesson Planning and Content.

1. Introduction

The teachers and the quality of their instruction are always the prime concern in education. The importance of language for learning cannot be overstated. Language underpins all school-based learning. Specifically, language allows pupils to participate in class, access the curriculum, negotiate academic literacies and succeed in examinations. A critical goal for proficiency-based learning is the elimination of persistent achievement and opportunity gaps. Proficiency-based learning can provide equitable, relevant, and rigorous learning opportunities that engage all students and foster the skills, knowledge, and habits of work necessary to be successful in the 21st century. Learners live in a global society where technology puts information at their fingertips and allows them to interact with others around the world in an instant.

Today's educational systems are responding to this ever-changing world by providing learning opportunities that require students to communicate effectively, engage in creative problem-solving, collaborate virtually and face-to-face, and apply critical thinking skills. Across the nation, our educational systems have not met the needs of all students. Vermont has joined with several other states to do something different. A proficiency-based educational system requires transparent expectations for learning where time is the variable and learning are the constant. This system includes explicit, measurable, and transferable learning targets that can clarify expectations necessary to demonstrate proficiency. Students and educators document learner progress; academic strengths and challenges are noted. Strategies and supports for meeting those challenges are identified and put into place. Globally, any educational institution is competent and well-performing teachers. In the teacher training institution, its main goal is to produce well-trained teachers who are ready to meet all the challenges in the actual field. The study of Yilmaz and Sahin (2019) revealed that most of the pre-service teachers strongly believed that proper understanding and hard work were more important than inherent ability and that acquired knowledge is important to be nourished. According to Saqr and Tennant (2018) global movement to rationalize school networks, the establishment of school clusters in certain countries and the expansion of the principles of new public management have contributed to re-centering analysis on the cultural and symbolic dimensions of the school, demanding new, more pluralistic perspectives, less bound by compartmentalized and one-dimensional views. students' abilities and lessons difficulties. With this, the university must continuously provide future educators with the appropriate and adequate knowledge, pedagogic skills, and readiness to make proper use of instructional facilities, suitable attitudes towards teaching, developing self-confidence and good attitudes, thus preparing them to be effective. According to the policies, standards, and guidelines for the Bachelor of Elementary Education, graduates must learn the needed competencies such as in-depth understanding of the diversity of the learner, comprehensive pedagogical content in various subject areas, utilization of different students' assessment tools, good communication skills and application of higher order thinking skills, demonstration of being a good model teacher, and willingness to upgrade professional growth (CMO, No. 74, series 2017). Different concerns related to their practice teaching were exposed such as teacher preparation practices, mentor-mentee collaboration efforts, and practicum experience necessary for aspiring teachers. For future teachers, according to Donaldson (2020), the teachers' responsibilities are always accompanied by accountabilities that made them afraid and considered the idea of "teaching to the test." However, there are still a lot of teachers who are trying their best to impart knowledge despite a lot of challenges in the classroom. Learning involves understanding, interpretation, reflection, and strengthening of current knowledge, experience, skills, values, concepts, and preferences. It is calculated through synthesize and following a pattern of growth and development of humans, animals, or other non-living objects. This should be taken as a process and not as a combination of facts and theories (Khalid, 2019). Today's teacher should be demanding of his students to preserve to achieve its objectives, to have success and eventually a good performance of his students at the end of a semester or school year. In the study of Matrosov (2019) also emphasizes that socialization, education, and development of student harmony are among the most important tasks of teachers. Presently, in the Philippines, a pre-service teacher will carry out practice teaching at his/her last stage of the teacher education program. A culmination of his/her formal education and the transi-

tional phase from being a student to becoming a future teacher. It aims to provide opportunities to apply the principles learned in the teaching-learning process; to discover their weaknesses in teaching; to gain a realistic picture of the teaching profession; to develop the skills and attitudes needed by the teacher; and to develop the skills needed to make the necessary adjustments to changing classroom conditions (Ocampo, 2021). Practice instruction is of utmost significance for the vocational preparation of student teachers. This immersion in the modern world of school prepares learners to switch from trainees to professionals. After finishing their education, several issues face the teachers who enter the workplace for the first time. Student teachers who apply for existing teacher preparation programs are not necessarily ready to reach the classroom. These issues are related to their classroom knowledge practice. Any student teachers tend to be inadequately trained for the actual situation during their teaching practice. The Philippine Constitution (Article IV, Section 23, Part 2) states that the objectives of tertiary education are: to train human power in the skills required for national development;

to instill and foster appropriate and relevant attitudes, skills, and knowledge; and to enable everyone to become a valuable, productive and knowledge-based member of society. If the Higher Educational Institution (HEI) graduates have the skills required to complete a teaching job, this provision may be implemented. It calls for a pre-service teacher to assess and evaluate his/her pedagogical skills required for the teaching climate of the 21st century. One of the issues mentioned in Flores (2017) study regarding the College of Development Education's employability in Region V is the poor foundation given to graduates as far as pedagogical competence is concerned. According to him, less time is given to graduates of the course to concentrate on the skills teachers should have in the 21st century. After the 21st century teaching scenario was given less time, the students enrolled in their subjects were more exposed to the content and training students regarding the various strategies tailored; therefore, the graduates produced under the teaching education program become knowledgeable in content to lack pedagogical preparation and exposure.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. According to Depra (2022), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascer-

tain their relationship. More to the point, Swart (2018) emphasizes that this method is used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses the teaching proficiency of public elementary

school teachers in Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. This is correlational since teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in ten (10) schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. The respondents were composed of 120-selected teachers of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the technology integration in teaching science and technological pedagogical content knowledge of novices' teachers at public elementary school. Random sampling technique was employed in this study. However, Kamunuan Elementary School, Aninipot Elementary School, and Gupitan Elementary School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools were equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study adapted a questionnaire on teaching proficiency which was patterned and adapted by the researcher from the Proficiency of Adult Learning Theory of Knox (1980) as cited by Magno (2019). He believed that proficiency as a unifying concept to relate acquisition of knowledge, skills, and attitudes to improved performance, which motivates much adult learning. Proficiency is the capability to perform given the opportunity. This was supported by the theory

of practicum by Malcolm Knowles (1982) as cited by Flores (2016). This theory posits that adults learn more effectively when: they are included in deciding what they need to know, the learning draws on their own experiences, they focus on tasks and problems rather than content, and. the learning experience is timely and relevant to their context. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher's preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. Validity of the instrument was ensured through expert's opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach's Alpha with the obtained values of 0.070. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, namely: teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools. Hence, the Cronbach's value of the construct met the minimum reliability of 0.796, it means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument's face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items teaching proficiency with the following: lesson planning, content, and teaching method. Part 2 pertained to the performance of pre-service teachers namely: competence, punctuality and work attitude. The perceptions of the respondents among the Langilan District teachers were based on the following Five-point Likert rating scales:

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following Five-point Likert rating scales:

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	The teaching proficiency is always evident.
3.40-4.19	High	The teaching proficiency is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The teaching proficiency is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Low	The teaching proficiency is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	The teaching proficiency is not evident.

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	The performance of pre-service teachers is always evident.
3.40-4.19	High	The performance of pre-service teachers is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The performance of pre-service teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Low	The performance of pre-service teachers is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	The performance of pre-service teachers is not evident.

The steps followed in the conduct of the study were:

1. Permission to conduct study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao Del Norte through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools.
2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent them back through researcher’s email-add or messenger.
3. Collection and statistical treat-

ment of data. The data were collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2020. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger, viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed, and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—

The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean. It was used to determine the level of teaching proficiency of public elementary schools in Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used in determining the

significant of teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools in Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. Multiple Linear Regression. This was utilized to determine the significant of teaching proficiency influence performance of pre-service of public elementary schools in Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the level of teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The level of teaching proficiency in terms of lesson planning, content, and teaching methods; the level of performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools in terms of competence, punctuality, and work attitude; and which of the factors of teaching proficiency significantly influence the performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte.

Summary on the Level of Teaching Proficiency. Presented in table 1 shows the summary on the level of teaching proficiency of public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. The indicator with highest mean is lesson planning with a mean of (3.96), interpreted as high. Then, it is fol-

lowed by content has a mean of (3.66) identified as high. Lastly, Teaching method has the least mean of (3.59) described as high. With an overall generated mean of (3.74) or high, therefore, the summary on the level of teaching proficiency of public elementary schools was high as perceived by the teachers.

Table 1. Summary on the Level of Teaching Proficiency

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Lesson Planning	3.96	High
2	Content	3.66	High
3	Teaching Method	3.59	High
Overall Mean		3.74	High

It can be gathered from the table that lesson planning, content, and teaching method were high. The teaching method was the least

among the indicators of teaching proficiency. This means that the engagement of learners in the lesson basically includes four dimensions.

These are behavioral, emotional, cognitive, and agentic engagement. Behavioral engagement is related to the observable features of the learners in the lesson. On the other hand, the necessity of developing students in many ways emerges. In this respect, it is important to raise individuals who actively participate in teaching activities and who have acquired scientific process skills. Considering this stated importance, the purpose of this study is to examine the effects of using different teaching methods on learners' class engagement and scientific process skills. Alternatively, in the subjects that learners have difficulty in understanding, their interest and engagement in the lesson decreases. Active learning methods should be used to prevent this situation (Türkben, 2015). Considering all the reasons, it

is concluded that it is both impossible and unnecessary for a person to learn everything. This situation makes it necessary to change the understanding of education. Since, teachers cannot teach everything, the shortest and rational way is to teach people how to learn (Çakır Sarıkaya, 2018). The teachers are the guide who actively manages the learning activities of his learners. In other words, a teacher-centered approach to a learner-centered education approach has switched. Instead, this situation forces learners to learn better. Because, they learn not only scientific concepts but also their relationships. Realization of these conditions causes learners to participate actively in class activities (Erbaş Demirer, 2019).

Summary on the Level of Performance of Pre-Service Teachers. Presented in table shows the summary on the level of performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. The indicator with highest mean is competence with a mean of (4.04), interpreted as high. Then,

it is followed by work attitude has a mean of (3.91) identified as high. Lastly, punctuality has the least mean of (3.87) described as high. With an overall generated mean of (3.94) or high, therefore, the summary on the level of performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools was high.

Table 2. Summary on the Level of Performance of Pre-Service Teachers

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Competence	4.04	High
2	Punctuality	3.87	High
3	Work Attitude	3.91	High
Overall Mean		3.94	High

This outcome is in consonance with the study of Asio and Riego de Dios (2019) wherein the respondents have a very good professional and personal quality. For Relojo, et. al., (2015) stressed that there was no significant relationship between emotional quotient and work attitude behavior. General evaluation of pre-service teachers' attitudes has yielded positive and high

results in a lot of studies. It is believed that pre-service teachers having high attitudes will also have job satisfaction, which will be promising for the future of the teaching profession. One of the factors influential on teacher achievement is their attitudes towards the profession. Teacher attitude influences a teacher's satisfaction with their profession, devotion to the profession, be-

belief in the necessity and importance of the teaching profession, and belief in professional development. Significant Relationship Between the Teaching Proficiency and the Performance of Pre-Service Teachers of Public Elementary Schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte

Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between the teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. Based on the analysis, the overall p-value is

equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.641. This means that there is a strong significant positive correlation between the teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. Hence, this study rejects its set null hypothesis. Furthermore, the analysis depicts that an increasing manifestations of teaching proficiency leads to an increased performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte.

Table 1. Significant Relationship Between the Teaching Proficiency and the Performance of Pre-Service Teachers of Public Elementary Schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte

Teaching Proficiency	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Lesson Planning	0.586	0.000	Reject
Content	0.525	0.000	Reject
Teaching Method	0.344	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.641	0.000	Reject

Specifically, the analysis in Table 3 highlighted the individual relationship between each indicator of the pre-service teacher’s teaching proficiency and their performance. Based on the analysis, the Lesson Planning indicator ranked as the top indicator of pre-service teacher’s teaching proficiency garnering a moderate significant positive correlation with their performance which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.586. This was followed by the Content indicator obtaining a moderate significant positive correlation with their performance which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.525. Lastly, is the Teaching Method indicator garnering a weak significant positive correlation with their performance which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.344. On the other hand, all of the indicators of pre-service teacher’s teaching proficiency show positive direct relationship to their performance of public

elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. This means that as the following indicators were increasingly manifesting by the pre-service teachers then their performance will also increase.

Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Pre-Service Teacher’s Teaching Proficiency on their Performance in Public Elementary Schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte.

As shown in the table 4, the overall analysis obtained p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 32.247 stating that there is a significant influence of pre-service teacher’s teaching proficiency on their performance in public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. This also implies that the regression model used in the analysis of the study is useful and that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influence.

Based also on the regression analysis of the study, two (2) out of the three (3) indicators of pre-service teacher’s teaching proficiency significantly influence their performance in public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. These pre-service teachers’ teaching proficiency indicators were the Lesson Planning indicator which obtained a t-value equal to 3.076 and a p-value equal to

0.000, and the Content indicator which obtained a t-value equal to 4.068 and a p-value equal to 0.000. With this finding, the set null hypothesis of this study that there are no indicators of pre-service teacher’s teaching proficiency significantly influence their performance in public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte is rejected.

Table 2. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Pre-Service Teacher’s Teaching Proficiency on their Performance in Public Elementary Schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte

Performance of Pre-Service Teachers Teaching Proficiency	Unstandardized Coefficients					Standardized Coefficients	
	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho	Interpretation	
Constant	1.009	.328	3.076	.003			
Lesson Planning	.403	.067	.447	5.997	.000	Reject Significant	
Content	.313	.077	.334	4.068	.000	Reject Significant	
Teaching Method	.055	.086	.051	0.643	.522	Reject Not Significant	

On the other hand, the Teaching Method indicator of pre-service teachers’ teaching proficiency does not significantly influence their performance in public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte since it obtained a t-value equal to 0.643 and a p-value equal to 0.522. Significantly, the established results of the regression analysis garnered an R2 equal to 0.656. This means that there are 45.5 percent ascribed to the significance influence between pre-service teachers’ teaching

proficiency that significantly influenced influence their performance in public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. Thus, the other 54.5 percent is ascribed to the other indicators not stipulated in the study. Particularly, these indicators could be included to determine that they might have stipulated influence to the performance of pre-service teachers in public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the level of teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the level of teaching proficiency in terms of lesson planning, content,

and teaching method. Moreover, this also identified the level of performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools in terms of competence, punctuality, and work attitude. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the level of teaching proficiency and the level of performance of pre-

service teachers of public elementary schools. Using non-experimental research, the level of teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service of teachers of public elementary schools was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public elementary school teachers in Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Theory of Know (1980) as cited by Magno (2019) and was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the level of teaching proficiency in terms of lesson planning, content, and teaching method was extensive. Similarly, the level of performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools in terms of competence, punctuality, and work attitude was high which means that it was sometimes manifested while in terms of teaching proficiency which also high. Hence, the level of performance of pre-service teachers as demonstrated by public elementary schools of Langilan District, Division of Davao Del Norte was high. Finally, indicators of management skills such as leadership, communication, and organization have significant influence of school heads performance of public secondary schools.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The teaching proficiency of pre-service of public elementary schools was high. The performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools was also high. There was a strong positive correlation between teaching proficiency and performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of teaching proficiency to the performance of pre-service teachers of public elementary schools: Lesson Planning and Content.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: The cooperating teacher-respondents must continue upgrading through postgraduate education. Since the cooperating teachers are responsible for training and mentoring the pre-service teachers, they must serve model to them. The pre-service teachers should learn more techniques on how to ask thought provoking questions to their learners and use the higher-order thinking skill art of questioning. The teachers handling professional subjects must continuously update their knowledge and skills so they can provide the competencies needed by the pre-service teachers in teaching.

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